

Titanium, Zirconium and Rare Earth Element Placer Deposits in Coastal Environments of Rías Baixas (Galicia, NW Spain)

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Rias Baixas is located on the northwestern coast of Spain, in the Galicia region (Fig. 1). They are part of a system of several funnel-shaped estuarine inlets, formed by tectonic action and subsequent erosion. Metamorphic and igneous rocks represent the geology of Rías Baixas in the study area, from Neoproterozoic to Early Permian age, which are favorable for the occurrences of primary critical raw materials mineralization, including Ti, Sn, Li, Au, and REEs. The Galineiro complex is the only known REE occurrence in the area, situated approximately 10 km south of Vigo City.

In the 1970s, IGME carried out the first exploration of shallow waters and beaches for heavy minerals forming placer deposits (IGME, 1976 and 1979). In 1991, GEOMY TSA studied sands in shallow waters in Galicia for beach nourishment, but geochemical data are not available (Mendez et al., 2000). Other research (Manso, 2001) reports the presence or absence of heavy minerals on the Galician coasts. In all these studies, the unit of measurement for heavy minerals is not weight %; nevertheless, due to the large number of samples, spatial distribution, and semi-quantitative reporting, we consider the IGME studies of the 1970s as the most representative for further investigation.

Fig. 1. Situation of Rías Baixas, NW Spain.

This study analyzes 1084 shallow-water samples (up to 100 m depth) and 461 beach samples (fine to coarse sand) for heavy minerals in placer deposits exploration, using GIS and geostatistic tools. Samples weighed from 5 to 8 Kg. Thiessen polygons were created with shallow-water samples to show the influenced area of non-continuous data. Heavy mineral concentration, originally reported in grams, was classified as follows: Class 1 = <1 g, Class 2 = 1-5 g, Class 3 = 5-50 g, Class 4 = >50 g, and Class 5 = absence. The geological and marine seabed layers are from GEODE (Geological Survey of Spain - IGME) and EMODnet-Geology, respectively.

In March 2023, S34i project partners visited 7 beaches in the Ría de Vigo (Limens-Santa Marta, Alemans-Ratas-Canabal, and Vao-Samil), and the heavy minerals have been identified as dark-brown and red color accumulations, in patchy distributions on the beach surface (up to 50 m²) and concentrated in 1 to 5 cm thick layers below the surface (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Santa Marta Beach in the Ría de Vigo. A) Dark patchy distribution of placers on the beach, B) heavy minerals at Santa Marta Beach. March 2023 exploration.

In beach samples (Fig 3), a detailed analysis of the high occurrences (mainly Class 4 and Class 3) of ilmenite, zircon, and garnet shows a strong relationship to metamorphic outcrops (mainly schist and paragneiss) close to beaches in two North-South bands surrounding an igneous rock body (granites, quartz diorite, and tonalite) presenting the same placer occurrences. It is very probable that the mineral sources are thin but abundant dykes in the coastal environment (observed during the field trip in March 2023), influenced by wave action for minerals accumulation. Monazite in beach sands appears only as Class 3 and is mainly found around igneous outcrops. Xenotime is very restricted to Cesantes Beach and its associated metamorphic outcrop, with this mineral occurring as an accessory in the glandular orthogneiss. Santa Marta Beach is the best place to accumulate ilmenite, zircon, garnet, and monazite. Xunqueiro-Fuchiños-Vao-Samil (Ría de Vigo) and Sagunto-Xiorto (Ría de Pontevedra) beaches are other locations where these minerals are concentrated.

In shallow-water environments (Fig 3), the occurrence of heavy minerals is lower than in the beach environment. Ilmenite and zircon occurrences are represented by Class 3, garnet by Class 3 and 4, and monazite by Class 2 with higher occurrences. For these minerals, high occurrences are not found within the Rias; on the contrary, they are generally found to the northwest of Ons Island. In this area, ilmenite and garnet appear in very continuous samples of Class 3, except for one sample of garnet, which belongs to Class 4 (63 g). Other isolated samples in shallow-water are located around Ons Island and to the north of Cíes Islands. The unique occurrence of monazite in Class 2 is to the northwest of Ons Island, and some continuous and discontinuous areas of Class 1 and absence can be found in the rest of the area.

Fig. 3. Mineral occurrences on the beach and in shallow-water for placer deposits in Rías Baixas. A) Mineral occurrence of ilmenite (Ilm), zircon (Zir), monazite (Mon), and garnet (Garn) for Class 4 (>50 g), and B) for Class 3 (5-50 g). Sampling stations from IGME (1979 and 1976) and S34i project (<https://s34i.eu/>).

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Likewise, when we plot the seabed layer from EMODnet-Geology in the northwestern Cíes Island, the highest content of ilmenite (Class 3) is observed in the sands and mixed sediment close to rocks and boulders on the seabed. Similarly, the highest content of garnet (Class 3 and 4) is observed in the coarse-grained sediment and mixed sediment. Although the nearest beach with similar content of both minerals is approximately 5 km in length, the source mineral is probably from the rocks and boulders on the seabed. Furthermore, more mineralogical and geochemical studies are needed to confirm this hypothesis.

In summary, this study shows the relationship between rock outcrops and the presence of heavy minerals, most likely influenced by wave action, for the beach placer (titanium minerals, zircon, monazite, xenotime, and garnet) in Rías Baixas. The preliminary results suggest a possible relationship between rocks and boulders on the seabed for the shallow-water placer (ilmenite and garnet) in the northwestern Cíes Island of Rías Baixas. Additionally, a higher occurrence of minerals was detected on beaches compared to shallow-water areas; garnet is predominant in most of the beaches; and the area with a lower mineral occurrence is located from As Mariñas to La Guardia (southern part of the study area) in both beach and shallow-water environments.

This study is a contribution to the Horizon Europe project S34i: Secure and sustainable supply of raw materials for EU industry (HORIZON-CL4-2022-RESILIENCE-01, Project 101091616, <https://s34i.eu/>).

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